

QUIZ

LAST NAME: MBA

FIRST NAME: ANTHONY

PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 7

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2018 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. It should do all the followings, except which one?**
 - It should have a thesis statement (answer to the question) and no argument.¹**
 - It should try to present or discuss something: to develop a thesis via closely points by reasoning and evidence.
 - An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.
 - It should answer a question or task.
- Why should anyone bother mentioning the source of where the information they are writing about came from? What is the harm?**

¹ "Essay Writing: The Basics | UNSW Current Students," accessed October 21, 2019, <https://student.unsw.edu.au/essay-writing-basics>.

- Plagiarism is wrong and ethical.²**
- It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
- It is a serious academic offense that can have consequences.
- In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to cite the author or source you are using.
3. **Long quotations take a different look. Quotations that are over four lines will be treated a little differently. Which one of the following is not a correct way to treat quotations that are over four lines?**
- They will always take quotation marks.³**
- They will take no quotation marks.
- They will be indented and look like a separate little paragraph.
- In the Euclid template, use the Quote Style.
4. **Which one of the followings is not one of the three kinds of questions that researchers ask?**

² "Essay Writing: The Basics | UNSW Current Students," 12–13.

³ "Essay Writing: The Basics | UNSW Current Students," 20.

- Special Questions: Answering so what?**⁴
- Conceptual Questions: What should we think?
- Practical Questions: What should we do?
- Applied Questions: What must we understand before we know what to do?
5. **Readers will expect you to use three different levels of sources. Which one of the following is not one of them?**
- Consult primary source for introductory overview.**⁵
- Consult primary sources for evidence.
- Read secondary sources to learn from other researchers.
- Read tertiary sources for introductory overview.
6. **By convention, you may omit the following types of sources from a bibliography, except;**
- Journal sources.**⁶
- Newspaper articles.
- The Bible and other sacred works.
- Well-known reference works, such as dictionaries and encyclopedias.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17–20.

⁵ Turabian, 24–27.

⁶ Turabian, 95.

7. Which one of the following statements is not true?

- Form the possessives of most singular common and proper nouns, including those that end in, x, or z, by adding an apostrophe and “s.” However, this rule does not apply to letters and numerals used as singular nouns, and to abbreviations.⁷
- Model your spelling on American usage and be consistent, except in quotations where you should usually follow the original spelling exactly.
- A colon introduces a clause, phrase, or series of elements that expands, clarifies, or exemplifies the meaning of what precedes it.
- The most common in presenting numbers is whether to spell them out in words (twenty-two) or give them in numerals (22).

8. One of the following is not a content of an entire dissertation?

- Introduction to Report Problem.⁸
- Literature Review.
- Research Methodology.
- Analysis and Interpretation of Findings.

9. In the lecture video titled, *Writing the Methodology Chapter*, Dr. Philip Adu, spoke about five main qualitative research approaches. Which one of the following is not one them?

⁷ Turabian, 63–88.

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Third edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2015), 31.

Ground and land theory Approach.⁹

Phenomenological Approach.

Narrative Approach.

Ethnography.

10. **During this semester, you were exposed to about four style guides, which of the following was not one of them?**

Kate Turabian rule of dissertation.¹⁰

WHO rule of style.

Blue Book (legal) rule of style.

European Commission rule of style or English Style Guide.

⁹ Philip Adu. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. March 6, 2016. National Center for Academic and Dissertation Excellence (NCADE). MPEG-4, 0.30
https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=189&v=KRHvxY3N708.

¹⁰ "ACA-401D Period 5 – EUCLID University LMS," MPEG-4, 0.7.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-5/>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.